

THE HISTORY OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF ART AND ITS SIGNIFICANCE IN HUMAN SOCIETY

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Abstract. *This article discusses the work carried out in the field of fine art from the time of the primitive community to the present, its development and its important role in the life of mankind.*

Keywords: *society, art, history, development, human, artists.*

People drew pictures of what they saw before they knew how to write. Images of primitive people carved on hoyas, cave walls and other places have reached our time. Images carved on such rocks were found on the banks of the Yenisei River, in Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Altai and other places. Based on the description of such simple pictures, the first writings were discovered.

Gradually, new processes of development began to appear in the field of visual arts of the ancient period. During this period, new discoveries were made in the field of fine art and its methodology. For example, even though painting lessons were not included in the course of general education schools during the renaissance period, a lot of innovations were introduced according to the method of teaching art in general education schools. Such artists created great innovations in the theory of fine art, boldly applied innovations in the field of painting methodology. Artists such as Chennino Chennine, Leon Batis Alberto, Leonardo da Vinci, who advanced in the field of drawing problems, made a great contribution to the field. Especially, their contribution to the construction of saharzakh of that time was incomparable. At that time, it was customary to decorate the buildings and streets of the most developed European cities with the works of these artists.

The characteristic features of the practical activities of these artists is that they collected the works of many ancient artists and studied their methods of work in the field of visual arts. Renaissance artists explained natural phenomena from a scientific point of view. Knowledge of proportion, perspective, and anatomy was the basis of the theoretical and practical work of artists of this period. The artists of the Renaissance period believed that drawing according to nature is the basis of painting education, and they created pamphlets and put forward this idea. In this field, Chennino 1said: "The great force that brings the artist into the palace of luxury is to paint according to the thing itself. This is better than copying. Trust him as soon as you see him, especially when you feel some feelings about the pencil image.

The great painter of the Renaissance, the wise Leon Batiste Alberto, says in the book "Treatise about painting" that "to learn to draw, one must first know geometry." He advises to study nature by imitating nature. Alberto says about young people learning to draw, "they should work like a person learning to write letters, that is, first they should learn letters, then syllables, and then words."

Leonardo da Vinci and Alberti say that painting should be viewed with great responsibility in the science of visual arts.

The artists of the Renaissance enriched the treasure of art knowledge with their works in the field of visual arts. For example, Dürer left the secrets of fine art not only to his students, but

also to all mankind, regarding the three-dimensional, three-dimensional objects in perspective. Since then, this knowledge has become a program for artists. The artists of the renaissance period generally thought a little less about some problems of pedagogy: teaching, education and other issues. Only in the academic period, scientists and artists began to deal more deeply with the issues of teaching and education in fine arts. Renaissance art education was conducted as follows. Boys were given to teachers from the age of 10-12. According to the information of Chennino Chennini in his scientific work on fine arts, children spend about a year drawing on a board, drawing for a year, then working with a teacher in the workshop, and making plasters, grinding plaster (primer) and leveling. , he had to learn all the work, such as running gold water, crushing, and these works were carried out in the artist's workshop. Artists had very few students. When the student cooperated with the artist's work, he got acquainted with his drawing materials and techniques, so the lessons were conducted in a practical way. Renaissance workshops were similar to Botti's scientific laboratory. Learning to paint in workshops was closely related to composition. The artist taught his student how to draw, but the art of painting was taught as a separate subject in the academies. The original work on the painting is attributed to Chennino Chennini. He writes: "The main way of the art of painting is to paint according to oneself." In order to learn the art of drawing, the student must work tirelessly. He says that painting should start with simple and easy things and practice more. Continuous practice leads to artistry. However, no matter how famous Chennino Chennini was, he also has certain shortcomings. Because it applies copying and especially copying to paper. After Alberti, Leonardo da Vinci continued the methods of painting. His work on painting was organized by his student, and after his death only scattered notes remained.

If we take a deep look at history, we can see that visual art plays the most important role in the culture, art, urban construction objects, culture and all other aspects of rural society. Today, if we pay attention to constructions in rapidly developing countries, for example, if you pay attention to day parks, hotels and offices being built in cities such as Singapore and Dubai, you will be sure that modern directions of fine art are widely used.

From what we have mentioned above, we can conclude that fine art has been developing and improving rapidly, like all other sciences, from the time of the primitive community to the present, and it still requires a lot of research in this field.

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